

Socio-Emotional Assessment of University Students in the Physical Education Course During the Pandemic

Prof. Dr. Francisco Evaldo Orsano¹, Evaldo Rodrigues Júnior², João Everton Pereira Rêgo³,
Débora Lopes Irene⁴, Nicole Macedo Orsano⁵

¹Docente da Universidade Estadual do Piauí – UESPI.

²Licenciatura Plena em Educação Física/ Universidade Estadual do Piauí – UESPI.

³Licenciatura Plena em Educação Física/ Universidade Estadual do Piauí – UESPI.

⁴Licenciatura Plena em Educação Física/ Universidade Estadual do Piauí – UESPI.

⁵Graduanda em Nutrição da Universidade Federal do Piauí – UFPI

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
08 September 2022

Corresponding Author:

**Prof. Dr. Francisco
Evaldo Orsano**

ABSTRACT

To evaluate the impacts of the pandemic on the socio-emotional state of university students of the Physical Education course at the State University of Piauí (UESPI) during the pandemic period. This research has a descriptive characteristic with a quantitative approach. The sample consisted of 39 students of both sexes. Due to the pandemic situation, it was only applied between the 5th to 8th periods. Participants responded to the socio-emotional self-assessment. The measures adopted were absolute frequencies and quantitative variables and means and standard deviation, as well as the Shapiro-Wilk test to verify that the data followed the distribution. (%). The difference between the standard components was Un for sample test for metric with two categories and Kruskal-W for three samples for samples with categories or more. It was observed that of the five socio-emotional skills, the female audience has the highest average in self-regulation, self-knowledge and responsible decision-making, reaching an average of 1.54; 1.93 and 1.79 respectively. The male audience reached the highest media in terms of social awareness and relationship skills, with the respective values being 1.53 and 1.53. The values presented in the standard deviation were respectively 0.204 in self-regulation, 0.013 in self, 0.101 in social awareness, 0.879 in relationship skills and 0.531 in decision making. The research points out that the Physical Education course at UESPI has a heterogeneous socio-emotional state, but the female audience reached a higher level than the male audience in 3 of the 5 socio-emotional skills.

KEYWORDS: Pandemic, Socioemotional, Self-regulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Organization the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the new Corona vírus (COVID-19) pandemic in march 2020 and soon it reached the world, from which the health authorities took several measures to mitigate the massification of the outbreak, such as adopting quarantine attitudes and expanding health services.

All these facts caused impacts of all kinds, from physical, economic, social domains and encompassing consequences for emotional health, such as anxiety, depression and stress (Talevi, et al., 2020; Kontoangelos et al., 2020). A study carried out in Greece (Patsali et al., 2020) revealed that two-thirds of university students said they had an increased level of anxiety after social isolation. In addition, studies reveal a high rate of anxiety, around 45% of all students (288) and

23% of university students with depression (Azevedo et al., 2020).

In research carried out by Kontoangelos et al., 2020, revealed that many factors can be associated with mental health during the pandemic period, such as loss of family income, lack of family support, lack of food, social life, feeling of fear, living with parents, were negatively related to anxiety traits. All this plays a role as a stressor, in which emotional regulation is necessary.

Social-emotional education (SES) is the process of acquiring skills necessary to manage and identify emotions, increase self-care and perceive others, establish affective bonds, make effective decisions and develop resilience to challenging situations (Weissberg, Goren, Domitrovich & Dusenbury, 2013). Based on these purposes, the Collaborative for

Academic, Social and Emotional Learning (CASEL) has developed programs for schools, with the aim of boosting five socio-emotional skills: self-awareness; self control; social consciousness; social skills and responsible decision making (Weissberg et al., 2013). The practice of ESE interventions in schools has been associated with good achievements, such as progress in academic performance, emotional skills, decreased levels of stress and attitude problems (Waldemar et al., 2016; Durlak et al., 2011).

Socio-emotional competence is defined as interpersonal relationship skills based on better self-knowledge and maturation. Allowing better emotional management in necessary moments (Santos, 2018). CASEL (The Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning) is an international non-profit organization formed by a large community of researchers, professors and several other professionals in the educational sector. And it aims to disseminate the result of socio-emotional learning throughout people's lives, as a way to promote healthy changes in society. The international organization CASEL says that socio-emotional competences can be determined by the ability to incorporate feelings, behaviors and thoughts in order to carry out social activities and social tasks and achieve concrete results in the personal sphere and in its cultural environment, in the biopsychosocial aspects.

Therefore, the purpose of socio-emotional learning is to provide an improvement in well-being, in learning in interpersonal relationships, in attitudes, in behavior, in decision-making for advances in quality of life and, in view of this, from now on, perspectives such as self-esteem, motivation, knowledge, individual risk and protection resources, life projects can be added (Frohmut, Nemer, Bérigamo and Ramirez, 2020).

Explicitly, the institution provides academic learning associated with a social and emotional education that instructs young people in an integral way to develop collaborative and socially responsible individuals to face future challenges (CASEL, 2020). It also adds that socio-emotional education needs to be disseminated and with an inclusive character for all in current times, a purpose that leads to believe that CASEL activities are so essential.

The concept of social and Emotional Learning (SEL) at CASEL is that social and emotional learning is a process of developing, acquiring and applying the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary to manage and understand emotions in a positive and healthy way.

According to the CASEL model (2015), socio-emotional skills are listed in five, such as self-knowledge, self-regulation, social awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision-making. In the new reality of teaching, socio-emotional skills have become more evident and consequently enabling the individual to better deal with the tribulations of the modern world (Schorn; Sehn, 2021).

All the students' means of conviviality have a positive role in the approach to learning and development in realizing the need and usefulness of their socio-emotional skills. Their skills can be improved and directed to provide possible better opportunities in the lives of young people and consequently in society (Ramazotti et al., 2020).

Abed (2016) states that it is impossible to prepare children and young people to face the difficulties arising from modern times without developing their skills to manage emotions, decisions, problem solving, manage information and deal with teamwork (Chaves; Haiashida, 2021).

In the search for the development of socio-emotional skills in educational institutions, it is necessary to focus on investment in teaching professionals, so that competences can be built in themselves and provide learning in a conscious and responsible way, recognizing and exercising the practice in its different ways. cognitive-affective states of their students and thus reaching the desired result (Abed, 2016).

Based on a recent meta-analysis, it was identified that, on average, 15.9% of children and adolescents exposed to traumatic situations of various natures end up developing Pre-Traumatic Stress Syndrome (PTSS), reaching 89% in cases of more intense traumas, thus causing a direct impact on the emotional and on their relationships in the social environment (Cahill et al., 2020).

Social-emotional skills, as mentioned earlier, help students to be able to give and receive good social rewards that, as a consequence, will expand their social interaction, since acceptance and popularity are assumed to be fundamental for socialization (Vale, 2009).

Taking into account the current reality, it is extremely important to be aware of the spread of anxiety and depression that intensified in the pandemic, so we can look at solutions for a mentally healthier life, preventing society from developing a problem in the following years. very serious in the psychological and interactive aspect (Lerman, 2020). This study aimed to evaluate the impacts of the pandemic on the socio-emotional state of university students of the Physical Education course at the State University of Piauí (UESPI) during the pandemic period. Thus, it is possible to get some idea of how they are currently and to contribute to students' self-knowledge about their socio-emotional skills.

II. METHODOLOGY

This research has a descriptive characteristic with a quantitative approach. According to Vasconcelos (2021), through research it is possible to reduce the subjective perspective and still develop a proximity between the object studied and its researcher.

The population of this study consisted of 39 students of the Physical Education course at the State University of Piauí (UESPI) Campus Pirajá in Teresina of both sexes, there was no filter or specific selection of individuals.

“Socio-Emotional Assessment of University Students in the Physical Education Course During the Pandemic”

For data collection, the questionnaire "socio-emotional self-assessment" requested on the Wordwall platform was applied, in which teachers are available addressing the socio-emotional skills listed in the CASEL model (2020), which are divided into five categories, such as self-knowledge, self-regulation, social awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision making.

Identify the socio-emotional skills of students through the data obtained by the questionnaire and make a comparison with the CASEL model (2020), which is based on socio-emotional skills, and what will determine which skills predominate in the student will be the number of answers accumulated in a area of each competence of the CASEL model (2020).

To describe the profile of the sample, absolute and relative frequencies were used in the qualitative variables and means and standard deviation, as well as the Shapiro-Wilk test to

verify if the data followed a Normal distribution (%). The difference between the questionnaire components was analyzed by the nonparametric U Mann-Whitney test for samples with two categories and Kruskal-Wallis for samples with three categories or more. Data were entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 20.0. The significance level adopted was $p < 0.05$.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sample consisted of 39 students of both sexes, the percentage of males was 51.3%, while the percentage of females was 48.7%, with the majority of participants under 24 years old, equivalent to 71.8 %. Due to the pandemic situation, it was applied only between the 5th and 8th periods (Table 1).

Table 1. Socioeconomic data of Physical Education students at the State University of Piauí (UESPI) in the pandemic period, 2022.

Variables	n	%	average ± DP
Sex			
Male	20	51,3	
Feminine	19	48,7	
Age			
Less than 24 years	28	71,8	23,10 ± 2,49
24 years or older	11	28,2	
Períod			
5	4	10,3	
6	5	12,8	
7	13	33,3	
8	17	43,6	
Income			
None	-	-	
Up to 1 salary	7	17,9	
1 - 2 salaries	18	46,2	
2 - 4 salaries	12	30,8	
More than 5 salaries	2	5,1	
Marital status			
Single	35	89,7	
Married	3	7,7	
Separated	1	2,6	
Fiance	-	-	

SD = Standard deviation

In table 2, it is observed that there were few variations of answers, and in the vast majority of questions more than 60% of respondents answered with the second alternative “Sometimes”, with the alternative “Always” there was an

average of 30% with a few exceptions reaching between 35% and 89%, with a single question reaching 97%. Going for the third alternative “Never” resulted in an average of 2.6% for the most part and presenting a single exception of 30%.

Table 2. Distribution of frequencies of the socio-emotional assessment questionnaire.

Questions	never	sometimes	always
1-Do I prepare everything I need before starting an activity?	1 (2,6)	25 (64,1)	13 (33,3)
2-Do I focus on what I'm doing?	1 (2,6)	24 (61,5)	14 (35,9)
3-If I make a mistake, do I try again?	-	15 (38,5)	24 (61,5)

“Socio-Emotional Assessment of University Students in the Physical Education Course During the Pandemic”

4-Do I insist until I finish my daily activities?	1 (2,6)	26 (66,7)	12 (30,8)
5-Do I feel satisfaction when I finish my activities?	-	4 (10,3)	35 (89,7)
6-When I start an activity, do I go to the end?	1 (2,6)	27 (69,2)	11 (28,2)
7-Do I like to do things I've never done?	1 (2,6)	25 (64,1)	13 (33,3)
8-Do I believe I can do everything they ask me to do?	2 (5,1)	31 (79,5)	6 (15,4)
9-Do I give up when I don't get what I want?	12 (30,8)	24 (61,5)	3 (7,7)
10-If I have difficulties, do I ask for help?	1 (2,6)	26 (66,7)	12 (30,8)
11-Music and dancing make me happy?	-	7 (17,9)	32 (82,1)
12-Am I happy when my friends are happy?	1 (2,6)	-	38 (97,4)
13-Do I like to meet new people?	-	17 (43,6)	22 (56,4)
14-Am I open to dialogue?	-	12 (30,8)	27 (69,2)
15-Can I organize time for leisure and rest?	-	20 (51,3)	19 (48,7)
16-Do I have physical and mental self-care?	2 (5,1)	21 (53,8)	16 (41,0)
17-Can I manage my emotions?	-	28 (71,8)	11 (28,2)
18-Can I exercise resilience?	-	26 (66,7)	13 (33,3)
19-Do I help people in need?	-	15 (38,5)	24 (61,5)

Table 3 shows the averages of individuals, regarding their perceptions of self-regulation, self-knowledge, social

awareness, relationship skills and responsible decision-making in relation to their sociodemographic situation.

Table 3. Components of the questionnaire according to the profile of university students at the State University of Piauí (UESPI) during the pandemic period, 2022.

Variables	Self-regulation	Self knowledge	Social consciousness	Relationship skills	Responsible decision making
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Sex					
Male	1,43 ± 0,23	1,71 ± 0,23	1,53 ± 0,37	1,53 ± 0,26	1,65 ± 0,49
Feminine	1,54 ± 0,19	1,93 ± 0,23	1,35 ± 0,21	1,5 ± 0,44	1,79 ± 0,54
p-value ^a	0,204	0,013	0,101	0,879	0,531
Age					
< 24 years	1,48 ± 0,21	1,82 ± 0,24	1,45 ± 0,33	1,52 ± 0,37	1,75 ± 0,44
≥ 24 years	1,50 ± 0,25	1,82 ± 0,30	1,42 ± 0,26	1,50 ± 0,32	1,64 ± 0,67
p-value ^a	0,678	0,842	0,818	0,89	0,528
Período					
5	1,42 ± 0,25	1,94 ± 0,24	1,33 ± 0,00	1,13 ± 0,25	1,75 ± 0,50
6	1,56 ± 0,16	1,80 ± 0,33	1,53 ± 0,19	1,70 ± 0,27	1,80 ± 0,45
7	1,58 ± 0,22	1,90 ± 0,22	1,44 ± 0,21	1,50 ± 0,35	1,77 ± 0,60
8	1,41 ± 0,21	1,74 ± 0,26	1,45 ± 0,43	1,56 ± 0,35	1,65 ± 0,49
p-value ^b	0,098	0,192	0,542	0,092	0,909
Income					
Up to 1 salary	1,53 ± 0,14	1,93 ± 0,28	1,57 ± 0,25	1,50 ± 0,41	1,86 ± 0,38
1 - 2 salaries	1,48 ± 0,22	1,86 ± 0,20	1,50 ± 0,35	1,56 ± 0,38	1,78 ± 0,55
2 - 4 salaries	1,49 ± 0,27	1,75 ± 0,30	1,28 ± 0,24	1,46 ± 0,33	1,58 ± 0,51
> 5 salaries	1,39 ± 0,08	1,50 ± 0,00	1,50 ± 0,24	1,50 ± 0,00	1,50 ± 0,71
p-value ^b	0,789	0,104	0,087	0,902	0,577
Marital status					
Single	1,48 ± 0,22	1,81 ± 0,25	1,46 ± 0,33	1,51 ± 0,35	1,71 ± 0,46
Married	1,48 ± 0,13	1,83 ± 0,29	1,33 ± 0,00	1,67 ± 0,29	2,00 ± 1,00
Separated	1,78	2,25	1,33	1,00	1,00
p-value ^b	0,323	0,28	0,66	0,269	0,281

^aMann-Whitney; ^bKruskal-Wallis.

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the impacts of the pandemic on the socio-emotional state of university students of the Physical Education course at the State University of Piauí (UESPI) during the pandemic period. Thus, it is possible to get some idea of how they are currently and to contribute to students' self-knowledge about their socio-emotional skills.

According to the CASEL (2015) model, there are five socio-emotional skills, namely self-knowledge (understanding one's own emotions, thoughts and values), self-regulation (managing emotions, thoughts and behaviors effectively in different situations), social awareness (understanding the perspectives and empathizing with others), relationship skills (establishing and maintaining healthy, supportive relationships and moving effectively in environments with diverse individuals and groups), and responsible decision-making (conscientious and constructive choices about personal behavior and interactions social).

This study highlighted that of the five socio-emotional skills, the female audience has the highest average in self-regulation, self-knowledge and responsible decision-making, reaching an average of 1.54; 1.93 and 1.79 respectively. The male audience, on the other hand, reached a higher average in social awareness and relationship skills, with the respective values being 1.53 and 1.53. The values presented in the standard deviation were respectively 0.204 in self-regulation, 0.013 in self-knowledge, 0.101 in social awareness, 0.879 in relationship skills and 0.531 in decision making.

In this conjecture, several studies point out that remote teaching, together with social isolation and immeasurable other factors in the period of contagion, pandemic, had a negative impact on the emotional health of Brazilian students, in particular university students. The health measures adopted in the pandemic period, such as social isolation, can be considered risk factors for the emotional health of citizens, presenting symptoms of stress, anxiety, depression, fear of contagion, boredom and anger (Schmidt et al., 2020).

In the sphere of socio-emotional skills, there is adaptability to the pandemic situation, but also anxiety and the absence of interpersonal relationships, which generate loneliness and stress (Fawaz & Samaha, 2021).

In the study by Alisic et al., (2020) they report that the psychological effects of the pandemic period and the stress caused by social distancing are notorious and can directly impact the emotional state of Education professionals and students. These at this moment hurt their mental health and well-being, as they are having to face some socio-emotional problems.

The results of this study showed that when analyzing the relationship between socio-emotional status and socioeconomic aspects, only males showed significant variation with socio-emotional skills, since females had higher levels than males in 3 out of 5 (self-regulation, self-knowledge and responsible decision-making).

In the studies by Carvalho and Silveira (2021), the main stressors in relation to the repercussion of the pandemic were changes in routine, distance from the socio-affective network, prolonged use of screens, a posture contrary to science and economic issues, in which students mentioned that family income was insufficient to guarantee quality of life, as well as the absence of a fixed income, job loss and the constant increase in food prices. Therefore, these difficulties may have a negative impact on the socio-emotional state of university students. Many families lost their jobs, making access difficult, especially food, which underwent constant readjustment, directly impacting the consumption of many foods, especially meat and fruits. About this agenda Galindo et al. (2021) recorded a decrease in meat (44%) and fruit (41%) consumption by adults in Brazil during the pandemic period.

For Ramazotti et al. (2020), conquering new socio-emotional and cognitive skills is the result of improving existing socio-emotional skills. Young people should be encouraged by their mentors to conquer their challenges, socialize and deal with stress. As a consequence, socio-emotional learning will be indispensable in academic and personal exercises.

This study showed that the average in the relationship skills category had a minimum standard deviation with values of 1.53 for males and 1.5 for females, resulting in a value of 0.879, which demonstrates that both sexes have a similar development in their relationship skills.

However, Gundim et al. (2021) cites that the restrictions caused by the pandemic period, conceived the need to deal with aspects that interfered in the relationship between people, such as the physical distance from friends, family and the restriction of touch, which caused changes in the emotional and psychic state of the students. Carvalho and Silveira (2021) also add that the routine during the pandemic was described as monotonous and repetitive by students, limited only to sleeping, performing domestic activities and attending online classes.

According to CASEL (2015) the teaching of socio-emotional skills is one of the most significant strategies available today to promote student success and effective educational reforms. The institution must be aware that cognitive ability alone does not meet all the needs that the world currently requires, as there are several studies proving that socio-emotional skills have a great influence on the academic performance of students (Mckown, 2020).

Some limitations that occurred with this study should be considered, such as the quantitative descriptive character, the availability of socio-emotional assessment questionnaires, which can be pointed out as the biggest obstacle in this research, and the use of instruments and questionnaires with subjective questions only of self-assessment, in the However, researches already carried out addressing the topic of socio-emotional assessment with instruments recognized and validated by the scientific community, have been widely

accepted and used. It can be noted that this descriptive study cannot be considered conclusive, therefore, we indicate models of studies with a greater number of population samples, to delve deeper into the topic addressed in this study.

IV. CONCLUSION

The research points out that the students of the Physical Education course at UESPI have a very heterogeneous socio-emotional status, but the female audience of the research reached an average higher than the male audience in three of the five socio-emotional skills, being self-regulation, self-knowledge and decision-making. responsible decisions, so their averages were lower in social awareness and relationship skills, despite getting an approximate value in the last socio-emotional competence mentioned above.

After the study, it was realized that it is necessary to develop the socio-emotional skills of students, as it is very important to alleviate inequalities in education and achieve full training. The pragmatic approach of professionals, as well as several scientific studies, make room for socio-emotional skills to have their space in the academic environment at the necessary moment, thus, the daily life of university students is directly affected in a beneficial way, leading to making good decisions within the academic environment. of their socializing environment.

REFERENCES

1. Abed, Anita Lilian Zuppo. (2016). The development of socio-emotional skills as a path to learning and school success for basic education students, Psychopedagogical construction, São Paulo, vol.24, no.25, set.
2. Alisic, E., et al. (2020). Rates of post-traumatic stress disorders in trauma-exposed children and adolescents: meta-analysis. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 204, 335–340.
3. Azevedo, Luiz Gustavo de; Silva, Davi Correia da; Correa, Alexandre Augusto Macedo; Camargos, Gustavo Leite. (2020). Prevalência de ansiedade e depressão, nível de atividade física e qualidade de vida em estudantes universitários da área de saúde. *Revista Científica UNIFAGOC, Caderno Multidisciplinar*, ISSN: 2525-488X, Volume I.
4. Brazil. (2017). Ministry of Education. Common national curriculum base – High School.
5. Brazil (2021). Ministry of Education. CASEL updates its definition of Social Emotional Learning. Vila Educação Institution.
6. Cahill, H.; Shlezinger, K.; Romei, K., Dadvand, B. (2020). Researching informed approaches to supporting student wellbeing post-disaster. Melbourne: Youth Research Centre.
7. Casel. (2015). Middle School Sel Resources. Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL).
8. Casel. (2020). Casel's sel framework. Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL).
9. Chaves, Caroline Martins; Haiashida, Keila Andrade. (2021). Approach to socio-emotional skills in remote teaching. *Teaching in Perspectives*, Fortaleza, v. 2, no. 3, p. 1-10.
10. Carvalho, Carla Jesus; Silveira, Maria de Fátima De Araújo. (2021). (About) experiences, mental health and coping with the pandemic of university students in socioeconomic vulnerability. *Research, Society and Development*, v. 10, no. 14, p. e288101421955-e288101421955.
11. Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child development*, 82(1), 405-432. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01564. x.
12. Fawaz, M., & Samaha, A. (2021). E-Learning: Depression, anxiety, and stress symptomatology among Lebanese university students during COVID-19 quarantine. *Nursing fórum*, 56, (1), 52-57.
13. Frohmut, Bruna Duarte Ferreira; Nemer, Elda Gonçalves; Bérghamo, Renata Oliveira Campos; Ramirez, Rodrigo Avella. (2020). The development of socio-emotional skills in high school and technical English language classes. *CB TecLE Magazine*, v.1, n.1, July.
14. Galindo, E., Teixeira, M. A., De Araújo, M., Motta, R., Pessoa, M., Mendes, L., & Rennó, L. (2021). Efeitos da pandemia na alimentação e na situação da segurança alimentar no Brasil. *Food for Justice Working Paper (Series, n. 4)*. Berlin: Food for Justice: Power, Politics, and Food Inequalities in a Bioeconomy.
15. Gundim, Vivian Andrade et al. (2021). Mental health of college students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Bahia Journal of Nursing*, v. 35.
16. Kontoangelos K, Economou M, Papageorgiou C. (2020). Mental health effects of COVID-19 pandemia: a review of clinical and psychological traits. *Psychiatry Investig.* [Internet]. [citado em 26 fev 2021]; 17:491-505. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.30773/pi.2020.0161>.
17. Lerman, Alexander. (2020). Socioemotional skills in mental health promotion. *Electi*, 21, Apr.
18. Mckown, Clark. (2018). Everything You Always Wanted to Know About SEL Assessment But Were Afraid to Ask. *Ed Surge*, 12, jun.

19. Patsali ME, Mousa DPV, Papadopoulos EVK, Papadopoulos KKK, Kaparounaki CK, Diakogiannis I, et al. (2020). University students' changes in mental health status and determinants of behavior during the COVID-19 lockdown in Greece. *Psychiatry Res.* [Internet]. [citado em 26 fev 2021]; 292:113298. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113298>.
20. Ramazzotti, Keila Maria; Galante, Keli Cristina Ramazzotti; Simões, Alquimar Geraldo. (2020). The importance of inserting socio-emotional skills in pedagogical practices. p. (1, 16).
21. Santos, Maristela Volpe et al. (2018). Socioemotional skills: analysis of national and international scientific production. *General, Rev. Interinst. Psicol., Belo Horizonte*, v. 11, no. 1, p. 4-10.
22. Schmidt, B.; Crepald, M. A.; Bolze, S.D.A.; Silva, L.N.; Demenech, L. M. (2020). Mental health and psychological interventions in the face of the new coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. *Rev. Psychology Studies*,37: 1-13.
23. Schorn, Solange Castro; Sehn, Amanda Schoffel. (2021). Socioemotional skills: reflections on school education in the context of the pandemic. *SciELO, Ijuí*.
24. Talevi D, Socci V, Carai M, Carnaghi G, Faleri S, Trebbi E, et al. (2020). Mental health outcomes of the CoViD-19 pandemic. *Riv Psichiatri.* [Internet]. [citado em 26 fev 2021]; 55:137-44. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1708 /3382.33569>.
25. Vale, Vera do. (2009). From weaving to mending: the threads of socio-emotional competence. *Higher School of Education – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra*, n.2 p. 132-133.
26. Vasconcelos, Isabela. (2021). *Quali-Quantitative Research: know and know how to apply. Your career.*
27. Waldemar, J. O. C., Rigatti, R., Menezes, C. B., Guimarães, G., Falceto, O., & Heldt, E. (2016). Impact of a combined mindfulness and social-emotional learning program on fifth graders in a Brazilian public school setting. *Psychology & Neuroscience*, 9(1), 79. doi: 10.1037/ pne0000044.
28. Weissberg, R. P., Goren, P., Domitrovich, C., & Dusenbury, L. (2013). *CASEL guide effective social and emotional learning programs: Preschool and elementary school edition.* Chicago, IL: CASEL.
29. World bank. (2020). *World bank group Covid-19 crisis response.* The World Bank, NW Washington.